

METHODOLOGY FOR DESIGNING COMPOSITE LAMINATE BOX BEAMS

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SUMMARY: This work describes the theoretical basis and design implementations for the prediction of the mechanical behaviour of fibre reinforced plastic box beams under various bending conditions. A computer assisted design package, called 'Buckle' has been developed as an aid for the design of these box beams. The design of the box beams is simplified with an inter-active approach to specifying constituent materials, overall geometric dimensions and loading situations. By incorporating an iterative approach, a comparison of materials and geometric structure leads to an appropriate selection and specification of fibre reinforced plastic beam performance requirements. The program implements a procedure for the prediction of the deflection and failure stresses in a box beam for a particular application. It enables the optimisation of fibre reinforcement orientation to minimise excessive deflections; determine buckling, and provides a comparison with similar behaviour of traditional structural materials

KEYWORDS: box-beam, bending, stiffness, deflection, computer-aided design

INTRODUCTION

Increasing use of fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) composites in structural applications is being made as manufacturing techniques, materials and improved analysis techniques are developed[1,2,3]. One reason that FRP composites are increasingly being used in engineering applications is their low specific mass compared to traditional construction materials such as steel and concrete. The low elastic modulus of FRP means that in structural applications it is best used where the shape of the member provides optimal stiffness[1,2,4]. For rectangular hollow box beams this is one of the most efficient forms of utilising FRP in terms of both stiffness and mass. These applications include stiffeners in the bodies of transport vehicles, interiors of boats and aircraft, ladders and office partition supports in buildings[5]. There is the potential to extend the use of FRP box beams further to include structural applications where the loads applied are higher and larger cross sections must be used. When using large beams, with thin walls, the chance of buckling occurring before the beam fails in shearing is high[6].

To achieve the appropriate combination of properties including lightness, resistance to deflection and buckling, the use of different laminate thicknesses or reinforcement orientation for different parts of the beam seems appropriate. In this work the authors developed a microcomputer based model for the design and analysis of laminated FRP box beams under

transverse loading conditions. A schematic diagram of the box beam configuration is shown in Fig.1 which also indicates the direction of applied loads and specific corner geometries. The computer design model enables the user to specify the composite material, or individual constituents, the arrangement of the plies and laminates, the angles of fibre reinforcement in the laminates and so optimise the geometry and material properties of the box beam. The results of the analysis provide appropriate guideline for beam strength, buckling resistance and weight for a given application. The program provides a comparison with steel, aluminium and timber beams of the same external dimensions. The model further enables prediction of the buckling and ultimate failure stresses in the beam to determine the suitability of that beam for a given application.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the (a) cross-section of a rectangular hollow beam - enlarged view and (b) overall depiction of the beam, indicating general load direction either as one or more point loads, or a uniformly distributed load(UDL).

STRUCTURAL APPLICATIONS

Traditionally, the major areas of use of fibre reinforced plastic composites in structural engineering have involved utilising the material in the form of laminated sheets. Most applications use the composite material either as a skin or as a roofing material which is stressed in tension or formed to support its own mass[1,2]. The use of FRP sections such as beams to support transverse loads much greater than the beam mass is less common. Investigations into efficient beam design has mostly been carried out for other structural materials. This is not surprising given the relatively recent emergence of sophisticated FRP composite materials[3,4].

In the civil engineering sector composite materials including concrete have been widely used for some time. Concrete is used primarily as a composite in its own right and as a macro-composite with the addition of steel reinforcement. Much work has been done in research, development and testing to optimise reinforced concrete beam sections for strength and weight[9,10,11]. This work has led to the widespread use of box beams of varying cross sections which are designed specifically against shear and buckling failure[11]. While the investigations into the use reinforced concrete box beams clearly show the advantages of optimising the cross section of a beam for strength, the methods used for the calculation of beam parameters are largely not applicable to other materials. Although design algorithms

used for reinforced concrete box beam design deal with transverse buckling conditions they tend to be highly specific in nature. Due to the high specific gravity of concrete combined with its negligible tensile strength, steel reinforcement is used in a different manner to that of the fibres in a FRP material. Steel is used primarily either to prestress the concrete or act as an externally supportive structural member.

Investigations into the design of FRP box beams determined the way in which fibre orientation in the flanges of a box beam reacted in its resistance to buckling[2]. This involved the fabrication of box beams each with differing laminate structures in the web, compression and tension flanges. The values of Poisson's ratio, longitudinal and transverse elastic moduli was experimentally evaluated from samples taken from the beams. The overall wall thicknesses were then measured and values for the second moment of for each beam were calculated. These beams were constructed with diaphragms included at regular intervals to avoid premature localised buckling at the point of loading. Theoretical critical buckling stress values for the top flange (compression), bottom (tension) and sides (web) of the beam were calculated using elastic stability theory and classical bending theory[6]. The beams were then tested for the mid span deflection under a load of 1.0 kN. All of the beams failed by buckling of the compression flange.

From the data obtained it was concluded that while the use of longitudinal reinforcement in the compression flange gave the lowest deflection, bidirectional reinforcement increased the resistance to buckling at the expense of ultimate longitudinal strength. It was found that the experimentally obtained results with one exception were within plus or minus 15% of the theoretical predictions. This showed that the behaviour of a laminated FRP box beam could be reasonably well predicted using elastic stability and classical bending theory as applied to experimentally established laminate properties.

An analysis of the optimum fibre reinforcement orientations in laminated plates for resistance to compression and shear buckling was carried out to study specifically the behaviour of symmetric laminates used in long simply supported plates[12]. Using the assumption that the stiffness of the plate was entirely due to the fibres, elastic theory was applied to determine the buckling characteristics of the plate - where theoretical optimum fibre orientation for compression buckling resistance was found to be with fibre alignment at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the longitudinal plate axis, though this arrangement gave a theoretical laminate compressive strength of zero. The optimum fibre orientation for resistance to shear buckling was found to be with $\pm 60^\circ$ fibre orientation, which this did not give maximum shear strength. This research showed that the theoretical optimum fibre orientations must be considered in conjunction with the strength characteristics of the laminate.

Investigations to describe the buckling behaviour of a reinforced plastic box section under axial loading were undertaken[13,14] with varying results. These approaches involved finding buckling coefficients which could be used to modify elasticity equations commonly used for the prediction of buckling behaviour of plates[6]. The equations obtained were then applied to predict the buckling characteristics of a unidirectional fibre reinforced plastic box section. No conclusion was drawn by the authors regarding the accuracy of this approach when extended to the box section, nor was there any experimental validation of the calculated results. These investigation were inconclusive regarding the application of equations modified by coefficients to the buckling of the box section.

Moreover, the buckling analysis of FRP box beams was often tedious and required many iterations for optimisation. To facilitate this analysis, a number of microcomputer programs are available which can be used for the analysis of the composite box beams under various loading conditions. These included programs which combine micro mechanical theory, classical laminate plate theory and a finite element analysis of the structure to generate solutions[15]. There remains the need for care when designing large section thin walled beams using these programs.

BASIS FOR THE CURRENT ANALYTICAL DESIGN PROCEDURE

The analytical design procedure adopted for this work on the mechanical performance of laminated FRP box beams is divided into two main areas. The first deals with the characteristics of the FRP material used for the beam construction whilst the second deals with classical bending and elastic stability theory to determine the buckling, bending and stresses of the loaded beam[6,8].

Characteristics of the FRP Material

Consider a FRP laminate as a structure composed of thin sub layers(lamina). The layers may have differing alignments of fibre reinforcement. The material properties of the FRP composite laminate properties may be established using a number of approaches; those utilised in this work are the well established micromechanical theories for strength and stiffness [1,2,3], i.e. elastic modulus, shear modulus specific gravity and Poisson's ratio. Whereas a macromechanical approach was employed to analyse the stress and strain relationships within a lamina. Plate laminate theory was utilised to calculate the laminate properties[7]. The strength of the laminate was determined using a quadratic failure criteria to establish upper and lower bounds[16,17].

Bending and Elastic Stability

Classical bending theory was used to determine beam deflection under a given load,. This is based on the longitudinal modulus of the material and the second moment of inertia of the beam cross section[6,8]. Calculation of the maximum compressive and tensile stresses and maximum bending moment in the box beam were carried out also using these classical bending equations. For a laminated FRP box beam having the flanges and webs made from different laminates, there is no common longitudinal modulus throughout the beam. To simulate an isotropic material the longitudinal elastic modulus of the compression flange is taken as a baseline. The mid equivalent or transformed thicknesses as function of the transformed moduli for the webs and tension flange were determined. These transformed thicknesses are used to calculate the second moment of area of the beam using the parallel axis theorem. Using the transformed thicknesses, the effective areas of the web and flanges can be calculated. In addition the deflection caused by the selfweight of the beam is considered as a uniformly distributed load. The mass of the composite beam is determined by applying the rule of mixtures to the specific gravities of the fibre and matrix constituents and multiplying the composite specific density by the beam volume.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE DESIGN

A computer program called "BUCKLE" was developed to predict the performance of laminated FRP box beams under transverse loading conditions. It provides information and guidelines about the viability of beams regarding resistance to buckling and failure due to exceedence of ultimate strength. Other outputs include the deflection of the beam compared with steel, aluminium and timber beams having the same external dimensions, and the performance of the steel, aluminium and timber beams with regard to buckling and ultimate strength. Shown in Fig. 2 is a flow chart of the major steps required in the design analysis. BUCKLE has been designed with an open program structure to allow the user to experiment by allowing the designer to quickly change parameters and observe the effects on beam performance.

Fig 2. Flow chart describing the design procedure

It is important to recognise that the designation of the tension and compression flanges depends on the loading condition applied to the beam. In this design procedure, simply supported and cantilever beams have the top flange as the compression flange while for cantilever beams the compression flange is the lower flange (as shown in Fig.1). A corner radius has been included in the program input parameters, as industry practice in making these beams is to employ a corner, radius to minimise stress concentration.

To enable the analysis of beams under a variety of situations, the program allows for five distinct loading conditions to be selected. These include, a simply supported beam with any of a point load, two point load or a uniformly distributed load (UDL), or a cantilever beam with any of point load or UDL. For each loading condition a schematic diagram is presented on the computer video screen so that a reference is available to ensure correct entry of data. Fig. 3 shows a sample screen of the format for the required data involved in the analysis together with a diagram of a cantilever beam with a uniformly distributed load. Any of the data may be amended, and further analyses carried out to determine new performance characteristics.

Fig. 3 A sample screen for the input of various beam configuration data and loading requirements.

RESULTS OF THE DESIGN PROCEDURE

Sample Analysis

A sample representative analysis of a composite beam was undertaken. The material selected was an E-glass epoxy such that the self-weight of the beam was 23.9 kg. The lamina was four plies thick with five repeats to give a total of 20 plies. The output data file combines the output data with the beam dimensions, laminate configuration, loading condition and material used. Included are the maximum deflections of the beams and the calculated critical and predicted stresses induced by the applied load.

Stresses in Composite Beam

The maximum strength of the composite beam is displayed according to the first or last ply failure modes[7]. These modes represent the failure stresses of the weakest ply and the

ultimate stress to failure of the laminate (ie the last ply in the laminate to fail) respectively. This data allows the designer to compare lower and upper bounds of the failure stresses in the laminates the stresses. Concomitantly, beam failure stresses are determined if failure is due to any of the buckling modes, or exceedence of the chosen strength criteria. For similar box beam steel and aluminium beams the stresses in the web and flanges together with the buckling stress is determined. A sample output of the stresses for the various beam materials is shown in Fig.4. For the timber beams (which are solid) only the maximum failure stress is determined.

LOADING CONDITION		
CANTILEVER BEAM - UNIFORMLY DISTRIBUTED LOAD		LOAD = 10 kN / m
STEEL BEAM - STRESS CONDITION		
	web shear stress	stress in flanges tensile & compressive
ALLOWABLE STRESS (BUCKLING)	252.9 MPa	1064.7 MPa
MAXIMUM STRENGTH	400 MPa	MPa
STRESS DUE TO LOADING	18.4 MPa	155 MPa
ALUMINIUM BEAM - STRESS CONDITION		
	web shear stress	stress in flanges tensile & compressive
ALLOWABLE STRESS (BUCKLING)	126 MPa	566.7 MPa
MAXIMUM STRENGTH	MPa	MPa
STRESS DUE TO LOADING	18.3 MPa	152.3 MPa
TIMBER BEAM - STRESS CONDITION		
	shear	tensile
MAXIMUM STRENGTH	MPa	MPa
STRESS DUE TO LOADING	19.6 MPa	1 MPa

Fig.4. Sample screen of comparative behaviour of beam materials.

Thus, the design analysis enables a comparison of failure behaviour to be made for the different materials at given loading conditions. Optimisation of the composite structure can be made by specification of varied materials and box beam dimensions.

Comparative Buckling Behaviour

For the present sample cantilever beam analysis, the critical buckling stress of the web is found to be 102 MPa and for the compression flange, 112 MPa. The web shear strength was 72 MPa and the compression flange strength 609 MPa. The web reinforcement was then set to $\pm 45^\circ$ with the flange reinforcement unchanged. The critical buckling stress of the web was shown to be reduced to 65 MPa while the beam deflected further than for the previous case. The web reinforcement was then set to $\pm 60^\circ$ and the compression flange reinforcement to $\pm 45^\circ$ which gave the highest values for the critical buckling stresses in both cases. The deflection of the beam under its own mass however was doubled from the previous case. The web shear strength remained constant but the strength of the compression flange was found to be less than one third of that for uniaxial reinforcement. Previous work has shown that the optimum fibre orientations for resistance to buckling was found in the compression flange to be $\pm 45^\circ$ and that for resistance to shear buckling in the web $\pm 60^\circ$, this gave the optimum

orientation for resistance to buckling. However, that these orientations did not provide for the maximum strength[2,12,13].

Comparative Deflection Behaviour

The deflection of a cantilever beam (as a rectangular hollow composite box structure) with a uniformly distributed load on the top surface, is compared with the deflection of similar beams of steel, aluminium and timber members with the same outside dimensions and interior geometries. A graph of the deflection of the composite beam versus distance along the beam is presented along with the deflections of the steel, aluminium and timber beams (Fig. 5). The deflections of the beams under their own mass may be obtained by setting the applied load to zero.

Fig. 5. Example of the comparative deflection of the different beams.

The results of the design iterative procedure indicate that the composite beam has an allowable deflection before failure of approximately ten times that of steel, and about six to seven times that of aluminium and timber. This design process is seen as a useful tool for the initial process in selecting appropriate beams, materials and geometries for specific loading conditions. Similar iterations may be carried out for other geometries, material combinations and loadings. Further design procedures for other loading conditions (point load and UDL on both a cantilever beam and a simply supported beam) indicated the benefits of using composite materials for the box-beams.

CONCLUDING COMMENTS

The investigations undertaken in this work led to the development of the BUCKLE program as an aid for the design of laminated FRP box beams. The computations of this program are based on well established bodies of theory which have in other applications been found to give good agreement with experimental results. Predicted results generated by the program should be used with caution. It is expected that further work in this field will be undertaken to determine the validity of the program output.

REFERENCES

1. Herakovich, C.T and Tarnopol'ski, Y.M., *Handbook- of Composites, volume 2, Structures and Design*, North-Holland, Amsterdam,1989.
2. Holmes, M. and Just, D.J., *GRP in Structural Engineering*, App. Sc. Pub. London, 1983.
3. Mallick, P.K., *Fibre-Reinforced Composites, Materials, Manufacturing and Design*, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 2nd Ed. 1993.
4. Benjamin, B.S., *Structural Design with Plastics*, Van Nostrand, New York, 2nd Ed., 1982.
5. Schwartz, M.M., *Composite Materials Handbook*, McGraw-Hill, New York,1984.
6. Timoshenko, S.P. and Gere, J.M., *Theory of Elastic Stability*, , McGraw-Hill, New York, 2nd Ed., 1961.
7. Tsai, S.W., *Composites Design*, Think Composites, Dayton, 4th Ed., 1985.
8. Roylance, D., *Mechanics of Materials*, J.Wiley and Sons, New York, 1996.
9. Abeles, P.W., *Prestressed Concrete Designer,-Handbook*, Viewpoint Publications, Stough, 3rd Ed., 1992.
10. Neville, A.M., *Properties of Concrete*, , Pitman, London, 3rd ed., 1991.
11. Bradford M.A. and Wong,T.C., "Local Buckling of Composite Box Girders under Negative Bending", *UNICIV Report No. R-292*, Univ. of NSW, Kensington, Oct. 1991.
12. Rothwell, A, "Optimum Fibre Orientation in Plastics and Polymers", *Fibre Science and Technology*, Vol. 2, No.3, 1969, p111.
13. Banks, W.M., and Rhodes, J., "The Buckling Behaviour of Reinforced Plastic Box Sections", *The Reinforced Plastics Congress '80*, Brighton, Nov. 1980.
14. Heitzer, J. and Feuch, M., "Buckling and Postbuckling of Thin Elliptical and Anisotropic Plates, *Computers and Structures*, Vol.48, No.6, 1993, p17.
15. Think Composites, A Division of ILT Corporation, Dayton, Ohio.
16. Sih, G.C., *Failure Mechanics of Composites*, North-Holland, Amsterdam, 1985.
17. Tsai, S.W. and Wu, E.M., "A general theory of strength for anisotropic materials", *J. Composite Materials*, Vol.5, 1962, p58.